

EFFECT OF REPROCESSING CYCLES ON MORPHOLOGY AND PROPERTIES OF ETHYLENE VINYL ACETATE (EVA) COPOLYMER/OLIVE HUSK FLOUR COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *EVA, olive husk flour, composites, reprocessing, EBAGMA compatibilizer.*

1 Introduction

The use of wood-based materials, such as wood flour and wood fibers, as reinforcing fillers for thermoplastics attracted a number of researchers and manufacturers during the last decade [1]. Indeed, the addition of wood flour as renewable natural filler in polymer composites aims to produce a unique combination of high performance, great versatility, light weight, recyclability, biodegradability and processing advantages at favourable cost [2,3].

Extrusion, injection and compression mouldings are the classical techniques for the processing of wood plastics composites [4]. However, the use of high processing temperatures coupled with intensive shear rates often result in degradation, which affects to some extent the performance of the materials [5].

Knowledge of microstructural changes arising from reprocessing of polymer composites is needed in order to find appropriate and useful applications of these materials and to evaluate their recycling potential [6].

Although a significant research work on the reprocessing of the most common polymers, including commodity polymers, engineering plastics, and composites is provided in literature, studies on reprocessing of wood composites based EVA copolymer are rather scarce [7].

Therefore, the paper is aimed to investigate the extent to which EVA copolymer/olive husk flour (OHF) composite materials are reprocessable in a single screw extruder in the absence and presence of ethylene/butyl acrylate/glycidyl methacrylate (EBAGMA) terpolymer used as compatibilizer.

The degradation induced by the recycling processes was evaluated through changes in molecular structure, morphology and tensile properties. The amount of the compatibilizer added to the composites was fixed at 10 phr of the total mixture of EVA/OHF: 70/30 w/w.

2 Experimental Part

2.1 Materials Used

EVA copolymer used as the composite matrix was produced by Arkema (France) and commercialized under the grade name Evatane @2805. It contains 18% vinyl acetate (VA) and it has a density of 0.939 g/cm³, a melting point of 89°C, and a melt flow index of 1.5 g/10 min.

The wood flour (WF) was extracted from olive tree originating from the region of Bejaia in Kabylia (Algeria). The wood particle shape is spherical with a maximum average diameter of 63 µm. The major constituents and the chemical composition of the wood flour were determined on the basis of absolutely dry substances using chemical procedures, i.e. cellulose = 58.34 wt. %, hemicelluloses = 17.20 wt. %, lignin = 23.92 wt. %, and mineral filler = 0.54 wt. %. The moisture content of the filler was = 6.20 wt. %.

The compatibilizer used was EBAGMA kindly supplied by DuPont (Belgium) under the trade name Elvaloy PTW.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Prior to blending, the WF was dried in an oven for 24 h at 105°C. Then the composites EVA/OHF were compounded with and without EBAGMA. Initially, compounding was carried out in a calendaring unit equipped with two-roll mill to produce films of almost 200 microns of thickness. The melt temperature was kept at 120°C and the mixing speed was 30 rpm. These milled composites were cooled by air and grinded. The objective of this processing step was to obtain an initial homogenization of the wood flour in EVA matrix. The granules were also dried at 105°C for 24 hours before extrusion. Both the pure EVA matrix and the composite materials were subjected to five successive mixing cycles using a Controlab-20D single screw extruder having an L/D ratio of 20. The barrel temperatures were chosen as 90, 110 and 130°C. The screw speed was 30 rpm. For each reprocessing cycle, samples were then extracted from the extruder and then compression moulded into plaques of 20 x 20 x 0.2 cm³ from which test samples were cut.

2.3 Characterization Techniques

FT-IR analyses were done on a Shimadzu 8400M FT-IR spectrometer. The film samples were scanned in the region 600-4000 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and 40 accumulations.

The mechanical behavior of EVA/OHF composites was analyzed by using a Zwick/Roell testing machine in tensile mode, with a load cell of 100 N capacity. Tensile tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. Five measurements were conducted for each sample, and the results were averaged to obtain a mean value.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed to investigate the morphology of EVA/OHF composites using a Quanta 200 instrument operating in environmental mode.

Water absorption was determined by measuring the difference from the weight at the initial time of the test and the constant final weight of the sample according to the following procedure: the specimen dimensions for water absorption experiments were 10×10×3 mm.

A minimum of three samples were tested for each material. Samples were first dried overnight at 70°C.

They were subsequently cooled in a desiccator at ambient temperature and weighted using a four-digital balance. Then, the samples were immersed in distilled water, pH = 6 and 25°C. After 24 hours, the samples were removed and blotted to eliminate the excess water on the surface. After weighting, the water uptake (WA) of the samples was calculated using Equation (1) [8]:

$$WU (\%) = [(M_1 - M_0)/M_0] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where M_0 and M_1 are the weights of the sample in mg before and after immersion in distilled water, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) analysis

The structural changes induced by the repeated extrusion cycles on EVA/OHF composites in the absence and presence of EBAGMA compatibilizer were investigated by FTIR spectroscopy. In Fig.1-a, FT-IR spectra of neat EVA, are presented in the range 3400-1600 cm⁻¹ after 1, 3 and 5 extrusion cycles. From Fig.1-a, it is clearly observed a superposition of all spectra indicating that no change in the chemical structure has occurred in the samples. This also means that EVA copolymer is chemically stable material after 5 extrusion cycles. Indeed, this behaviour is expected regarding the fact that polyolefins are generally known to be thermally stable. However, in Fig.1-b, which shows FT-IR spectra of neat EVA recorded in the range 1200-800 cm⁻¹, a slight increase in the absorption band intensity at $\lambda_{max} = 1023 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is noticed from the third cycle. This absorption band is generally attributed to the asymmetric stretching vibrations of ether groups (C-O-C) [9,10]. Under certain conditions, ether groups may initiate cross-linking reactions.

Fig.2 shows FT-IR spectra of virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites recorded in the range 4000-800 cm⁻¹ after 1 and 5 extrusion cycles compared with neat EVA. All spectra indicate that no noticeable changes have occurred in both virgin and compatibilized composite samples up to 5 extrusion cycles suggesting a good stability of the composite materials. This could be also due to

the presence of lignin in OHF acting as a thermal antioxidant by trapping the free radicals formed during the repeated extrusion cycles [11].

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of neat EVA copolymer after 1, 3 and 5 extrusion cycles recorded in the regions: (a): 3400-1600 cm^{-1} and (b): 1200-800 cm^{-1} .

Fig. 2. FTIR spectra of neat EVA, EVA/OHF and EVA/OHF/EBAGMA composites after 1 and 5 extrusion cycles recorded in the range of 4000-800 cm^{-1} .

3.2. Morphological analysis by scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Fig. 3-a shows the SEM micrograph of fractured surface of EVA/OHF composite sample after 1 extrusion cycle. From Fig. 3-a, it is observed the presence of OHF aggregates randomly dispersed in the polymer matrix. Further, some microvoids and cracks are also apparent on the surface. This morphology is somewhat expected due to the incompatibility between the filler and the matrix.

On the other hand, Fig. 3-b,c,d and e shows the fractured surface of EVA/OHF composites after 2, 3, 4 and 5 extrusion cycles, respectively. The morphological analysis indicates clearly that the number of microvoids, as well as the size of OHF aggregates have decreased with increasing the number of extrusion cycles, thus suggesting a better dispersion of the filler in the polymer.

The compatibilization effect of EBAGMA in EVA/OHF composites is well illustrated in Fig. 4-a. It can be observed that the morphology of the compatibilized samples is characterized by a regular surface and a significant reduction in the size of OHF aggregates in comparison with the virgin one.

Moreover, This morphological improvement results probably from interactions between OHF and EVA and it seems to be favoured with increasing the

number of extrusion cycles as shown in Fig. 4-b, c, d and e. Indeed, SEM analysis indicates an homogeneous dispersion of the lignocellulosic filler in the polymer matrix. The presence of some fracture lines on the surface of the composite materials is due to the method of cutting the samples in nitrogen.

From Fig. 4-b, c, d and e, it can also be observed that the size of OHF particles decreases as the number of repeated cycles increases.

This behaviour is consistent with the data reported by Kaci et al. [4] in their studies on the effects of repeated extrusion cycles on polypropylene/wood flour composites in the presence of EBAGMA compatibilizer. The authors explained this behavior as a result of either the occurrence of partial degradation of the polymer matrix, or the increase in extent of the reaction between the functional groups of the EBAGMA compatibilizer and the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose. In this latter case, a better interfacial adhesion could be obtained as a result of reprocessing.

Fig.3. SEM micrographs of EVA/OHF: 70/30: (a): 1 cycle, (b): 2 cycles, (c): 3 cycles, (d): 4 cycles and (e): 5 cycles. X 2400.

Fig.4. SEM micrographs of EVA/OHF/EBAGMA: 70/30/10: (a): 1 cycle, (b): 2 cycles, (c): 3 cycles, (d): 4 cycles and (e): 5 cycles. X 2400.

3.3. Tensile measurements

The determination of mechanical properties of polymers, especially modulus and strain allows to evaluate the extent of degradation undergone by the materials during aging process. In this connection, Fig. 5 shows the variation of Young's modulus as a function of number of extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized composite materials in comparison with the neat EVA copolymer. Initially, the Young's modulus of neat EVA is almost 40 MPa and this value has increased by approximately 55% in EVA/OHF composite samples. This increase is attributed to the substitution of the matrix EVA by the cellulosic filler, which is more rigid, thus limiting the mobility and the deformability of the macromolecular chains of EVA. However, this

addition of EBAGMA seems to reduce slightly the Young's modulus of EVA/OHF composites.

Fig.5. Variation of Young's modulus as a function of number of extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites compared with neat EVA copolymer.

result could be attributed to the decrease in the stiffness of the composite material as a result of the butyl acrylate group of the compatibilizer acting as an impact modifier. However, it is observed in Fig. 5 that for both virgin and compatibilized composite samples, the repeated extrusion cycles has no noticeable changes on Young's modulus, although slight variations are observed during recycling of the composite samples.

For the neat EVA, the effect of the number of extrusion cycles on Young's modulus is negligible.

Fig. 6 shows the variation of stress at break of virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites as a function of number of extrusion cycles.

From Fig. 6, it is observed that the value of stress at break is 20 MPa for neat EVA. The addition of 30 wt.% of OHF in the polymer matrix results in a sharp decrease in the value of stress at break of the composite material to 8 MPa.

This behavior may be attributed to bad dispersion of the filler in the matrix and a weak interfacial adhesion between the components.

Fig.6. Variation of stress at break as a function of number of extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites compared with neat EVA copolymer.

However, the presence of 10 wt.% of EBAGMA compatibilizer in EVA/OHF composites results in a slight increase in the stress at break from 8 to 9 MPa. In general, this very small increase may be related to a better interfacial adhesion between the components of the composites. Whereas, the effect of the number of extrusion cycles on neat EVA induces a slight decrease in the stress at break after the fifth cycle to reach the value of 17 MPa. For both virgin and compatibilized composites, the stress at break is almost unchanged with increasing the repeated extrusion cycles.

Fig. 7 shows the variation of elongation at break as a function of number of extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized composites compared to neat EVA. From Fig. 7, it is observed that initially, there is a decrease in elongation at break for all composite materials in comparison with the polymer matrix. EVA copolymer is a very ductile material exhibiting higher elongation at break of about 717 %. The addition of 30 wt.% of OHF to the polymer matrix leads to a brittle composite material. This behaviour is well expected due not only to the rigid nature of OHF, but also to possible occurrence of some chemical interactions between the filler and

the polymer matrix. Consequently, there is a restriction in the mobility of macromolecular chains resulting in poor deformability of the material.

Fig.7. Variation of elongation at break as a function of number of extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites compared with neat EVA copolymer.

However, from Fig. 7, the effect of the repeated extrusion cycles on the elongation at break of EVA copolymer is almost negligible up to the third cycle. But, after this, it is observed a slight decrease in the initial value of elongation at break by almost 11%. According to Khan et al. [12], this may be explained as a result of thermo-mechanical degradation of the material leading to a decrease in both stress and strain at break. Fig. 7 shows also that the repeated extrusion cycles seem to have no effect on both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites in the first three cycles. However, after 4 and 5 cycles, a slight increase in elongation at break is observed which can be attributed to better interfacial adhesion minimizing the formation of microvoids and other defects.

3.4. Water uptake

Water uptake data measured as a function of the repeated extrusion cycles for both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites in comparison with the neat EVA are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of water uptake at equilibrium for virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites compared to neat EVA as a function of number extrusion cycles.

Water uptake (wt %)	Number of cycles				
	1	2	3	4	5
EVA	0.14	0.14	0.13	0.12	0.12
EVA/FGO	2.13	2.36	2.84	2.62	2.32
EVA/FGO/EBAGMA	1.98	1.89	1.91	1.96	1.64

From Table 1, it is observed that the initial value of water uptake of EVA copolymer is almost 0.14 wt.%. This value remains almost unchanged within all the repeated extrusion cycles. Indeed, EVA is a hydrophobic thermoplastic. However, the incorporation of 30 wt.% of OHF produces an increase in the percentage of water uptake of the composite material by 93% passing from 0.14 wt.% for EVA to 2.13 wt.% for the EVA/OHF composite. This result is well expected because as the amount of OHF increases, the concentration of hydroxyl groups (-OH) increases too and subsequently, the hydrophilic character of the composite material is enhanced [13,14]. Further, it is also noticed that the effect of the repeated extrusion cycles on water uptake of EVA/OHF composite is somewhat limited since only 8% of increase are observed after five cycles. This result is consistent with the data reported by Najafi et al. [15]. The authors attributed this phenomenon in composite materials based on recycled polypropylene and polyethylene filled with wood flour to the capacity of the interfacial region to absorb water. Therefore, it is necessary to use coupling agents in order to improve the affinity between the filler and the matrix. However, the addition of EBAGMA to EVA/OHF leads to a decrease in the percentage of water uptake of the composite material by almost 8% passing from 2.13 % for virgin EVA/OHF composite to 1.98 % for the compatibilized one. This indicates clearly that some hydroxyl groups of the cellulosic filler have reacted with EBAGMA resulting in less hydrophilic material. Further, it is also observed from Table 1 a sharp decrease in water uptake for the compatibilized sample after five extrusion cycles by approximately 17% due probably to the occurrence of more interactions between all components of the system EVA/OHF/EBAGMA.

4. Conclusion

From this study, it can be concluded the following: FTIR data reveal that no noticeable changes have occurred in both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites after five extrusion cycles. This may be attributed on one hand, to the thermal stability of EVA, and on the other hand, to the lignin present in the filler which acts as a thermal stabilizer by scavenging the radicals. Further, SEM analysis indicates better dispersion of OHF in EVA matrix during recycling.

The tensile properties, especially Young's modulus, stress and elongation at break for both virgin and compatibilized composite samples remain almost unchanged during the repeated extrusion cycles in comparison with neat EVA. Moreover, the study shows that the compatibilized EVA/OHF composites are less hydrophilic than the virgin ones. Finally, the whole results show clearly that both virgin and compatibilized EVA/OHF composites can be recycled at least five times without altering the functional properties. This is very interesting from both industrial and technological point of view.

5. References

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